

COSMETICS CAN HARDLY ALTER THE INHERITED LOOKS : A CASE OF CONVERSION OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Aim of the study: The purpose of writing the paper is to see whether the objective of conversion of an HEI is justified or not. There is no intent to criticise any one.

Design/methodology/approach: The case study method has been adopted. The required data and information have been collected through secondary sources.

Findings: The paper contains the concepts related to change management. Besides, a case study is also included for the purpose of analysis to learn the perceptions, opinions, and viewpoints of the stakeholders to see whether the decision of conversion of institutions has been justifiable.

Practical implications: The paper provides the stakeholders with a scope of analysing the case for the purpose of improving upon the quality of higher education.

Originality/value: The paper is related to higher education. Thus it has social relevance and implications. For the growth of a nation, the quality of education needs to be ensured. The paper puts focus on maintaining the quality of education in general and higher education in specific.

Paper Type: Case Study

Keywords: Change, Management, Higher Education, Institution, Conversion

Culture does not change because we desire to change it. Culture changes when the organization is transformed – the culture reflects the realities of people working together every day.

- Frances Hesselbein

1. INTRODUCTION

Change is the rule of nature. Change means a shift from status quo. (Shaikh Ahmad, 2020) states in his paper that as the competition grows and markets shrink due to tougher economic challenges, decision and policy makers require to understand the importance of constantly evolving to remain competitive. This is also essential for them to retain their employees as well as customers. A Higher Education Institution (HEI) is also susceptible to change as it is an open system; it consistently affects and gets affected by the external environment in which it operates. Every organization/institution ought to be ready to change as per the need of the hour if it longs to survive and sustain. There is an urgent need on the part of the owners/top management to continually scan the external environment so as to smell a shift in it and respond befittingly to adapt to the shift. There can be a variety of forces/drivers/antecedents that can necessitate change. Some of the external environmental forces are: political, socio-cultural, economic, legal and technological. Besides, certain factors as government, customers, suppliers etc. can also be the part of the external environment that can drive change.

2. RELATED CONCEPTS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Types of change

Organizational/Institutional changes can be of various types. They are planned/well-thought/well-meditated change. Planned change means activities that are intentional and purposive in nature and designed to fulfil some organizational/institutional goals. Unplanned/poorly meditated change means shifts in organizational activities on account of forces that are external in nature; these are beyond the organizational control (Greenberg and Baron, 1997). First order change is continuous in nature. The focus is more on to be adaptable to routine kind of changes in order to improve upon the functioning of an organization/institution. Second order change is fundamental in nature and involves major shifts generally across the institutions covering almost all the aspects of the functioning of an institution.

There may be other nomenclatures of the types of change as Adaptive Change, Innovative Change, and Radically Innovative Change (Tyagi, 1997). Adaptive Change introduces or reintroduces the change which is conversant in nature. Innovative change relates to the introduction of a new practice to an organization. Radical innovative change focusses on the introduction of a practice new to the industry. If we put all three changes on a continuum from low to high sequentially, the degree of complexity, cost and uncertainty and probability for resistance to change move from low to high.

2.2 How to change in a planned way?

Kurt Lewin's Force-Field Analysis is an effective strategic means used to comprehend the fact as what pushes and what boomerangs change (Lewin, 1951). In a change situation there can be two types of forces operative. Forces that propose and support change are called the driving forces and forces that oppose and hinder the change are termed as restraining forces.

If the driving forces are stronger than the resisting forces the change will take place otherwise the status quo will be maintained.

Kurt Lewin has propagated a change model/process which helps in introducing/implementing change in an organization/institution in an effective manner (Lewin, 1951). The model has three phases as Defreezing/destabilizing the status quo, changing/moving to a new state of change and refreezing the new state of change. Defreezing state implies recognition of need for change and motivation to change. Changing means moving from status quo to new state of change is endeavouring/putting forth efforts to create change and refreezing occurs when resistance to change is managed and people start stabilizing the desired state of change.

2.3 Why change is resisted?

There may be multiple reasons responsible for resisting change. They may primarily be segmented in two categories: Personal or Individual and Organizational/Institutional. Personal reasons that can be attributed to resistance to change are-misperceiving the need for change, fear of unknown, new learning, disruption of long and fast relationships, fear of economic loss, opposition for the sake of opposition, loss of status and identity/job insecurity, habit of saying no even if the change is for good, communication gap, losing grip on things, work shirking attitude and so on.

The organizational causes for change can be-structural inertia, organizational politics, climate of mistrust, lack of well thought plan and poor timing, inadequate efforts to spread awareness, lack of competency and confidence, inadequate focus on change, fear of hidden agenda of owners and top management and so on. The resistance to change can be hidden, silent and indirect also.

2.4 Managing resistance to change

Change is the only factor which is constant and natural. Resistance to change is also usual. Certain well meditated efforts can be put forth to manage resistance to change. These can be- Do the adequate homework to handle the resistance, Chalk out a checklist, conduct a pilot/feasibility study, identify the root causes responsible for resistance, deploy the right resistance handlers, educate and train people, involve people in the process of change, facilitate and support, feedback and review/follow-up and so on so forth.

2.5 Checklist

Seek answers to the following questions so as to make it sure that the change will be introduced effectively:

1. Is the change required?
2. Are the organizational/institutional systems and procedures flexible enough to facilitate the change?
3. Have you ensured that the existing culture will not be a case of culture misfit?
4. What kind of approach reactive or proactive needs to be resorted to?
5. Are you aware of the consequences of the change?

6. Are you mentally and physically prepared for introducing change?
7. Have you conducted an opinion survey to ascertain the feasibility of the change?
8. Have you devised the apposite strategies to introduce and implement the change?
9. Have you spread adequate awareness about the change in the organization/institution?
10. Have you made it sure that top management is fully willing to support the change and committed to it?
11. Have you planned to see that the participative/democratic style of leadership/management will be adopted?
12. Have you planned for designing an effective education cum training program so as to mitigate and manage the resistance to change?
13. Are you determined to make a feedback and follow up to guarantee that the desired change is properly stabilised?

2.6 Top management support and success of change interplay

The said interplay is highly intervening in making it sure that change will be successfully introduced or not. It needs to be ensured that the change management is not presumed to be a vicious circle rather it is accepted as a virtuous cycle by the organization. The vicious circle carries the negative connotation and worsens the situation with the passage of time, whereas, the virtuous cycle results into the increasing beneficial effect of a phenomenon. We will see both the situations in terms of change management separately to learn about them in a better manner through the figure-1 vicious circles and virtuous cycle.

Figure: vicious circle

Virtuous Cycle**3. Epilogue**

In fine, it can be said that change is inevitable. As an individual and institution we ought to be ready to accept the change particularly when it is for betterment and there is need of hour. Change occurs within and outside the organization. Resistance to change is likely. Lot of reasons can be attached to the resistance to change. In the lack of communication people do not get willing to change. An enlightened and efficacious leader can ensure successful implementation of change. If potential barriers to change are acknowledged in prior, a change road map is duly prepared, awareness is boosted and stakeholders are taken into confidence through devising apt strategies for change, the likelihood of success gets augmented. The purpose of writing the paper is not to question the governmental policies, procedures and decisions, rather the purpose is to facilitate in making the administrative/managerial systems effective so as to justify the actions/decisions taken by the concerning governmental agencies and authorities in the domain of higher learning. As per Mr. Barak Obama, “Change will not come if we wait for some other person or some other time. We are the ones we’ve been waiting for. We are the change that we seek”.

4. Case Narrative**4.1 Primer**

Various higher educational institutions as universities, colleges and other centrally and state funded institutions are engaged in the process of imparting education in the field of higher learning. Ministry of HRD, Government of India resorted to a decision to covert a few

existing state universities in to central universities. The term conversion was also named as upgradation and elevation. In fact, many States wanted to have central university, some of the States wanted to have more than one central university. However, there was resistance from certain sections of the society to converting Goa University in to a Central University; rather there was persuasion to create a new Central University in addition.

4.2 Institutional profiles

The exercise literally started with the conversion of Allahabad University on 24 June 2005. Consequently, in view of increasing access and improving upon the quality of higher education in the country, the 11th Five Year Plan as approved by the National Development Council (NDC) envisioned establishing one Central University in each of the States that did not have any Central University till then. Thus, 16 Central Universities were set up in view of the Central Universities Act, 2009 in different deprived States.

On 15th Jan., 2009 few state universities as Guru Ghasidas Vishwavidyalaya in the State of Chhattisgarh, Dr. Harisingh Gour Vishwavidyalaya in the State of Madhya Pradesh and Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal University in the State of Uttarakhand were also upgraded as central universities.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Key issues involved

The changed institutions dealt with the issues related to culture misfit, lack of apt mind set, leadership quality, institutional politics adjustment of staff and property, overlapping of state and central university rules and procedures, disaffiliation of affiliated colleges and so on.

The Central Government started a new centrally sponsored Scheme, Rashtriya Uchchatar Siksha Abhiyan (RUSA) which would see to incentivize the State Governments so as to improve higher education by creating additional capacity in existing institution and set up new institutions in unserved and underserved areas. Under this scheme, the State Government would have the flexibility to set up new Universities and Colleges keeping in mind the local requirements.

The Ministry has made it categorical that no demand from the State Governments for the conversion of State Universities into Central Universities will be considered. Crunch of funds and quality control cannot be the sufficient explanations for conversion. As Central University is a unitary entity in nature, the conversion of a State University into a Central University is a herculean task.

One of the reasons that were attached to conversion was backwardness of the area due to lack of industrialization and private participation in the field of education. The experience of Government of India about the conversion has been bitter. It observed that after the long span of conversion the converted State Universities could not meet the expectations with which they were converted. Rather they fetch a variety of hitches as ego clashes, deteriorating quality of higher education and research, culture misfit, sense of marginality and so on so

forth. Even after the lapse of long-time from conversion they could not get rid of their legacy encumbrances.

With regard to the conversion of the State University into Central University, the Ministry of HRD has taken a policy decision not to convert State Universities into Central Universities for certain reasons as inheritance issues, adjustment of present staff and disaffiliation of affiliated colleges and so on.

6. Conclusion

The converted institutions have become marginal in nature. They are neither able to leave the old trends nor they are competent enough to adopt the new ones. People working in these institutions are facing the problem of culture misfit. There are professional, transitional, ethical, socio-cultural and political issues to be addressed. Two of the converted institutions were under the scanner of investigating agencies. The difficult period of transition could not be dealt with properly.

The views generated through the probable answers to the following questions based on the perceptions of education providers, educators, students, consultants and those who have interest and expertise in the field of higher learning will create a basis for weighing the decision of converting an existing state university in to a central university and to see that the said action has been justifiable or not.

7. End questions

1. What kinds of strategies were devised to guarantee the successful introduction of change?
2. Was there a need to design a training program to facilitate the change targets to be willing to accept the change?
3. Would you put the case either under the category of reactive or a proactive change?
4. What suggestions would you like to make if you are hired as a consultant and how these suggestions would help in resolving the problems?
5. What are the key issues involved in the case?
6. Was there some urgency or earnest need to introduce the change?
7. What change drivers/forces/antecedents did you find responsible for the change?
8. Who was/were the change agent(s) in initiating the change in the case?
9. If you were in place of the change agent(s) what would have been your actions/decisions?
10. What are the driving and restraining forces?
11. What power tactics were adopted to introduce change?
12. What kinds of measures need to be taken now by the present leadership/management to make the functioning of the converted institutions effective?
13. What grounds for resistance to change do you notice?
14. Was the resistance to change managed meaningfully?
15. Is the change management culture bound? Explain.
16. Is introduction to change episodic in nature? Comment.

17. Do you agree that the change will be adopted faster when it comes to the question of survival?
18. What power strategies were adopted to introduce change?
19. Evaluate the effectiveness of change program in the light of concepts discussed in the case? What kind of bottlenecks gets surfaced?
20. Last but not the least, whether the leading purpose of change was served or defeated?

8. Limitations and future Research

The study is secondary data based. Secondary data have their own limitations. A research study for learning the current state of affairs with regard to conversion can be conducted. The study can be primary as well as secondary data based.

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